

RESILIENCE MODEL IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study is to understand resilience models and its role in school teacher. The present study focuses on different models of resilience for enhancing sustainability of teachers in the school. The study focuses on the use of important indicators of resilience required for professional development of the teachers. The role of mentor (senior teachers) in supporting teachers and enhancing resilience is important aspect of the study. The study emphasizes fostering resilience in school teachers with the help of mentor teachers and support networks with practical solutions for the problem.

Key words: *fostering resilience, mentor teacher, support network.*

INTRODUCTION:

Resilience is the process and outcome of successfully adapting to difficult or challenging life experiences, especially through mental, emotional, and behavioral flexibility and adjustment to external and internal demands. There are many factors that contribute to individual's adapting ability in the problem situation like

- (a) the ability of an individual to observe the problem situation,
- (b) the availability and quality of social resources,
- (c) specific coping strategies.

Psychological research demonstrates that the resources and skills associated with more positive adjustment (i.e., greater resilience) can be cultivated and practiced. There are several theories and frameworks that contribute to the theoretical background of resilience.

Lindsey Smethem and Philip Hood (2011) had written a chapter in the seminar series on *Beyond Survival Teachers and Resilience*. These seminar series were on topics like *Fostering Resilience through Initial Teacher Education and Fostering Resilience through teacher support network etc.* Each chapter in this seminar series is divided in to sections like situation, resilience in this context and practical Example of fostering resilience.

Fostering Resilience through Initial Teacher Education

Novice teachers are helped to build resilience with the help of mentors of their schools

- A. To establish realistic roles and responsibilities of mentors and pre service teachers who are undergoing teacher education programme.
- B. To understand the challenges encountered during learning to teach and reasons for these and to find realistic and individualistic solution for the same.
- C. To maintain a respectful relationship with the mentor.
- D. To critically analyze their own beliefs, values and practices.
- E. To work in collaboration and cooperation in improving teaching and learning process.
- F. To value teacher well being.

The mentor's role is as follows

- To give support, feedback and advice to the novice teachers.
- To appreciate personal and emotional attributes of the novice teachers.
- To understand the challenges in learning to teach.
- To encourage the novice teachers through as a resourceful mentor.

Practical solutions to the novice teachers

- To do self evaluation of teaching by watching video analysis of teaching
- To acknowledge the open, honest and sensitive communication in challenging professional teacher education.
- To have good support system with the peer and B.Ed. teachers.
- To work in collaboration and cooperation with peer.
- To appreciate the role of peer in others development so that they will also appreciate you in return (reciprocity).

Fostering Resilience through Teacher Support Networks

Kevin Armstrong and Julian Stanley (2011) worked as the Teacher Support Network and provide the service of counselling through telephone communication. The service is free and confidential which provide the emotional support to all teachers in England, Scotland and wales.

Context: This was an example of a teacher whose resilience was boosted by phone counselling support, provided by Teacher Support Network (TSN). TSN provide free and confidential practical and emotional support to all training, serving and retired teachers in England, Scotland and Wales. To explain the Resilience in this context an example of

conflict between a novice teacher and HOD of the school. The novice teacher was in great distress due to conflict with HOD and colleagues. The role of the counsellor through TSN was to provide the courage to cope the distress and resolve the problem. the TSN Counsellor give moral boost by assess how to respond emotionally and practically in this conflict situation. Various coping strategies were discussed and gave suggestions in changing her routine with healthy eating habits, regular exercise, yoga workout, sleep enough, and over well being of herself.

In the subsequent sessions, the teacher was more confident and calm and ready to implement new strategies for her improvement. On Reflecting on the Resilience, health, wellbeing and work effectiveness all are interrelated, and should be fostered with experience personals.

Benjamin T. L. (2012), this research was based on the novice special education teachers of rural area of Hawaii island. the researcher had used the resiliency theory to understand the novice special education teachers problems and challenges with protective and risk factors in term of administrative and collegial support system. The researcher has used case study design where in the five participants were interviewed for their personal experiences as a novice teacher. The views of the novice teachers were in regards to the support from administration, interaction with colleagues, expectation, recognition, teaching assignments and time required. This study describes experiences of novice special education teachers in rural areas in Hawaii through a lens of resiliency theory. Two types of support – administrative and collegial – were examined in terms of being risk or protective processes. A case study design was used to give voice to five participants who expressed their satisfaction and concerns about support from administrators, interactions, expectations, recognition, teaching assignments, meetings and time. The study examined support from general and special education colleagues, school staff, and outside service providers. Qualitative analysis was carried out which is shown below in the flowchart.

Figure No. 2.4: Benjamin T. L. - Qualitative analysis

The Reflective Model

The Reflective Model is based on the basic assumption that teachers develop their professional proficiency through reflecting on their own practice. In other words, a teaching experience is recalled and evaluated so as to provide input to improve and help in future planning and action.

Wallace's Reflective Model is applicable to both pre-service and in-service teachers. The model is divided into three stages:

The pre-training: The candidates who have enrolled themselves into teacher training courses and decided to take this professional education does not enter the programme with blank mind. The student has, at least, some pre-training knowledge about teaching, learning and assessment.

The Professional Development: This is the stage where the main professional education and development of the student-teachers happened through theory and practice. Student teachers or teachers plan, practice and reflect on their experience to improve the process.

The Professional Competence: The final goal of this model is to increase professional competence through reflective practices. Figure given below shows the process of reflective Model:

FIGURE 2.5: Reflective Teacher Education Model

Wallace presents the Reflective Model as a cyclical process in which the trainees are involved throughout their teaching experience. Such a cycle aims at continuous improvement and the development of personal theories of action.

Caroline Mansfield (2014) this article focused on the challenges faced by the early career teachers in their first years of teaching and how these challenges are managed for saving their careers. It also studied different literature based on resilience and then

developed a model of early career teacher resilience. In this model the resilience is looked as a process on the edge of personal and contextual challenges and resources. The study was conducted on Australian teachers with a data collection tool used was a semi-structured interview to understand the challenges faced by 13 Australian early career teachers and the resources available to manage these challenges are examined. After data analysis, it was found out that early career teachers face problems varied type of challenges and personal and contextual resources are important for retaining them in their profession. The study also highlighted the importance of family and friends to support teachers in building their resilience.

Caroline Mansfield (2016) this articles states that online learning resources are effective way to build teacher resilience among the preservice teachers. it also helps to make them ready for classroom teachings. The BRiTE resources are very effective online modules for training the preservice and in-service teachers to develop resilience. The modules give a positive approach with usefulness of the content and resources designed. This module helps the teachers to enhance their efficacy as it has resilience focused approach”.

According to Caroline Mansfield, this module is very personalised, interactive, connected to the profession and grounded in the literature, the BRiTE resource may complement teacher education experiences and have the potential to support not only pre-service teachers and B.Ed. teachers, but also practising teachers.

Indicators of Resilience

Following are the important indicators of resilience which were reviewed and studied by the researcher:

1. Resilience is well studied and researched concept in the western countries as compared in India.
2. Resilience is cognitive process which depends upon the internal and external factors of a person.
3. Resilience components have strong base in cognitive psychology and Neuropsychology.
4. Resilience is nurtured, developed during the times of stressful situation.
5. Internal factors like skills, character, mindfulness, hardiness, emotions, feeling, empathy, sense of purpose, determination, positive mental attitude, ability to handle stress, communication skills, understanding the situation and reacting accordingly to name the few.

6. Resilience is affected by external factors like environment, upbringing, parents, friends and peer members.
7. Resilience is described as emotional stamina of an individual.
8. More the person is resilient the more he/she will succeed.
9. Resilient people are very flexible, are ready to adapt new surroundings, develop themselves in adversities.
10. Resilience is also applicable to the organization to sustain in the difficult times of the business and markets.
11. Resilience is about accepting reality, constructing meaning from reality and then improvising ability
12. Resilience can be fostered through practising mindfulness (concentration on breathing process with allowing thoughts to enter mind) and by practising yoga activities.
13. Resilience is related to self efficacy
14. Resilience is related to emotional intelligence
15. Resilience is related to hardiness

References

- Best, J., & Kahn, J. V. (2005). *Research in Education (9th ed.)*. New Delhi: Prentice – Hall of India.
- Benjamin, T. L., & Black, R. S. (2012). *Resilience Theory: Risk and Protective Factors for Novice Special Education Teachers*. *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*, 5, 27.
- Smethem, L. & Hood, P. (2011). *Beyond Survival Teachers and Resilience*, Univeristy of Nottingham
- Wallace, L. R. *the what, how and why of emotionally intelligent reflection*.
- Gillespie, B. M., Chaboyer, W., & Wallis, M. (2007). *Development of a theoretically derived model of resilience through concept analysis*. *Contemporary nurse*, 25(1-2), 124-135.
- Mansfield, C., Beltman, S., & Price, A. (2014). 'I'm coming back again!' *The resilience process of early career teachers*. *Teachers and Teaching*, 20(5), 547-567.
- Mansfield, Caroline (2021). *Cultivating Teacher Resilience: Introduction*, 10.1007/978-981-15-5963-1_1
- Crane, M. F., Searle, B. J., Kangas, M., & Nwiran, Y. (2018). *How resilience is strengthened by exposure to stressors: the systematic self-reflection model of resilience strengthening*. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping*, 32(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10615806.2018.1506640>
- Le Cornu, R. (2013). *Building Early Career Teacher Resilience: The Role of Relationships*. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 38(4). <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2013v38n4.4>
- Mansfield, C., Beltman, S., Weatherby-Fell, N., & Broadley, T. (2016). *Classroom ready? Building resilience in teacher education*. *Teacher education: Innovation, intervention and impact*, 211-229.
- Mangal, S. K. (2006). *Advanced educational psychology*. New Delhi: Printice hall of India Private Limited.
- Masten, A. S., Best, K. M., & Garmezy, N. (1990). *Resilience and development: Contributions from the study of children who overcome adversity*. *Development and Psychopathology*, 2(4), 425–444. doi:10.1017/S0954579400005812
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Richardson, G. E. (2002). The metatheory of resilience and resiliency. Journal of clinical psychology, 58(3), 307-321.

Huisman, S. E. (2007). Preservice teacher efficacy: The influence of field placements. University of Missouri-Saint Louis.